

PYRUS Soccer Simulation 2D Team Description Paper 2024: Zone-Based Defense Strategy

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Abstract. In the dynamic and evolving field of robotic soccer simulation, the Cyrus Soccer Simulation 2D team has consistently distinguished itself through groundbreaking strategies and robust performance, culminating in a laudable record at the RoboCup worldwide competitions. This paper introduces an innovative defensive strategy, devised by our sub-team, PYRUS, which seeks to further our legacy of excellence in the forthcoming IranOpen 2024 competition. Departing from traditional man-to-man marking schemes, our novel approach emphasizes zone-based defense, assigning each agent the responsibility for monitoring and defending a specific area determined by their formation position. This strategy leverages spatial analysis and dynamic positioning to optimize defensive coverage and adaptability, reflecting our commitment to advancing the strategic complexity and effectiveness of soccer simulation algorithms. Through this paper, we present the theoretical underpinnings, algorithmic design, and preliminary results of our zone-based defense system, aiming to contribute to the broader discourse on tactical innovation in robotic soccer simulations. Our history of success, including four first-place finishes at IranOpen and a distinguished record at the RoboCup, underscores our ongoing pursuit of excellence and innovation. By sharing our latest defensive methodology, we invite the community to explore the potential shifts in competitive dynamics and strategic planning this approach may herald.

Keywords: Soccer Simulation · RoboCup · Defense Strategy.

1 Introduction

Soccer, a game of profound strategy and physical prowess, stands as the most popular sport globally, captivating millions with its blend of team spirit, individual skill, and competitive dynamism. This widespread appeal has not only elevated soccer to a cultural phenomenon but also positioned it as a fertile ground for research and innovation, particularly in the realm of robotics and artificial intelligence.

Enter RoboCup, an international scientific initiative with the ambitious goal of developing a team of fully autonomous humanoid robot soccer players capable of winning against the FIFA World Cup champions by the year 2050. This visionary project serves not only as a challenge to the fields of AI and robotics but also as a platform for advancing research in these areas, fostering collaboration, and pushing the boundaries of what is technologically possible.

Within the RoboCup framework, the Soccer Simulation 2D League offers a unique environment for exploring complex multi-agent systems, artificial intelligence strategies, and computational theories. In this league, teams of autonomous agents operate within a two-dimensional virtual soccer environment, where they must make real-time decisions based on incomplete and noisy sensory information, execute sophisticated team strategies, and adapt to the dynamic nature of the game. This simulated setting provides a controlled yet challenging domain to test and refine algorithms for autonomous agent behavior, cooperation, and competition.

A critical aspect of soccer, both in the real world and its simulated counterpart, is defense. Traditional strategies often rely on man-to-man marking, where each player is tasked with closely guarding a specific opponent. However, in the context of the Soccer Simulation 2D League, this approach presents significant challenges. The inherently multi-agent environment, coupled with varying observational capabilities and perspectives of each agent, can lead to confusion and inefficiency in selecting which opponent to mark. Furthermore, the high computational complexity of dynamically assigning opponents to mark, combined with the limited "energy" available to simulated players, exacerbates the limitations of man-to-man marking, reducing its effectiveness and strategic viability.

2 Background and Related Works

In this section, we highlight some of the most innovative approaches and strategies developed by Soccer Simulation 2D (SS2D) teams in recent years.

YuShan2022 introduced an offline training model combined with the LambdaMART algorithm to enhance their team's attacking capabilities, specifically focusing on improving movement direction decisions[4]. RobôCIn developed an adaptive strategy that adjusts based on the current time, score, and the opposing team's pressure, alongside the creation and release of a log analyzer tool[5]. The Persepolis team made significant enhancements in key areas such as passing, shooting, dribbling, and marking, and employed a ranking algorithm to bolster their chain-action tactics[6]. Additionally, Persepolis integrated a Path Planning algorithm to refine their offensive maneuvers[7, 8].

Helios2022 embarked on numerical experiments to evaluate the impact of utilizing Anonymous mode on match outcomes[9]. HfutEngine2D explored genetic algorithms for parameter optimization and experimented with neural networks for more sophisticated decision-making processes, achieving marked improvements in their performance during trials against other RoboCup teams[10]. Al-

ice2D focused on defense optimization, leveraging Monte-Carlo tree searches and reinforcement learning algorithms to enhance their defensive strategies[11].

The Hades2D team dedicated efforts to bolstering the offensive and defensive capabilities of their individual players, resulting in a notable reduction in the average goals conceded[12, 13]. FRA-UNITed applied reinforcement learning techniques to enhance their players' proficiency in intercepting the ball, establishing a Markov decision process (MDP) environment featuring an agent learning to intercept and a player executing dribbling actions. This setup facilitated the agent's progressive improvement in interception skills[14].

These contributions underscore the vibrant innovation within the SS2D community, reflecting a continuous pursuit of excellence and strategic sophistication in the realm of robotic soccer simulations.

3 CYRUS and PYRUS Achievements and Previous Works

In this section, we delve into the historical research and development undertakings of the CYRUS team since its inception in 2013, highlighting the evolution of our strategies and contributions to the Soccer Simulation 2D (SS2D) community.

3.1 Achievements

To showcase the impressive achievements of the CYRUS team across various competitions, this section highlights our remarkable successes and the impact of our contributions to the field of Soccer Simulation 2D. Throughout our participation in the RoboCup and other prestigious competitions, CYRUS has consistently demonstrated excellence and innovation, achieving notable success:

RoboCup Achievements: Our team claimed the championship title in 2021, showcasing our leading-edge strategies and team coordination. We secured second place in the years 2018, 2022, and 2023, reflecting our persistent presence at the top of the competition. In 2019, we achieved third place, further cementing our status as a formidable force in the RoboCup community.

Japan Open: In 2020, we were proud to achieve second place at the Japan Open, a testament to our team's adaptability and strategic depth on an international stage.

Asia-Pacific Competitions: Marking our influence in the Asia-Pacific region, we won first place in 2018, demonstrating our excellence and innovation in robotic soccer simulation.

Iran Open: Our team has shown outstanding performance in the Iran Open, winning first place in 2014, 2018, 2021, and 2023. These victories are a clear indicator of our leading position within the local competition. In 2022, we secured second place, maintaining our consistent performance and competitive spirit.

These achievements not only highlight the technical prowess and strategic innovation of the CYRUS team but also our commitment to excellence and continuous improvement in the evolving field of robotic soccer simulation. Our success across various platforms reflects our dedication to pushing the boundaries of what is possible in Soccer Simulation 2D, inspiring both our team and the wider community to strive for greater heights.

3.2 CYRUS Team’s Research Evolution

Founded in 2013, CYRUS has consistently engaged in diverse research areas within the SS2D domain, beginning with the development of advanced passing behaviors, innovative unmarking strategies, and tactical formation adjustments[15, 16]. Progressing further, our focus expanded to enhancing defensive tactics[17], refining shooting algorithms, and improving team communication[18]. By 2017, we ventured into the realm of opponent behavior prediction, an effort that continued into the following years, yielding significant advancements in pass prediction, unmarking modules, and the creation of the Data Generator framework[19–23, 25, 26]. Our commitment to community development and knowledge sharing has led to the release of several key projects, including the Cyrus2D Base code and the PYRUS - Python SS2D Base Code, among others.

Significant Contributions by CYRUS

Cyrus 2014 Release: Following our notable performance in the 2014 RoboCup, finishing fifth, we made our source code publicly available. This repository serves as a valuable resource for teams seeking insights into competitive strategies and implementations, accessible via our GitHub⁴.

Cyrus2D Base Code: The Cyrus2D Base, a synthesis of the best features from Helios Base[28], Gliders base[29], and our own championship-winning strategies, offers a comprehensive starting point for teams entering the SS2D league. This foundational code is designed to expedite the development of RoboCup-related projects and is available on our GitHub⁵.

PYRUS Base Code: Tailored for teams keen on integrating artificial intelligence within their strategies, the Pyrus Base provides a Python-based platform conducive to Machine Learning algorithm development and testing. This base code is accessible via our GitHub⁶.

Cyrus AutoTest2D and AutoTune2D: Building on the foundation laid by the WrightEagle team[30], we enhanced the Cyrus AutoTest2D software to facilitate extensive parallel game testing. Alongside AutoTest, the AutoTune2D tool

⁴ Cyrus 2014 Source <https://github.com/naderzare/cyrus2014>.

⁵ Cyrus Base Source <https://github.com/Cyrus2D/Cyrus2DBase>

⁶ Pyrus Base <https://github.com/Cyrus2D/Pyrus-SS2D-Base>

enables precise parameter optimization, aiding researchers in maximizing team performance. Both tools are available on our GitHub^{7, 8}.

Cyrus Log Analyzer: This tool offers comprehensive analysis of SS2D game logs, providing teams with critical statistical insights such as pass counts and dribbling frequencies. Such analytics are invaluable for strategy refinement and performance optimization, available on our GitHub⁹.

These initiatives reflect CYRUS's dedication to pushing the boundaries of research in the SS2D league and our commitment to fostering a collaborative and innovative community.

4 Zone-Based Defense Strategy

In the realm of Soccer Simulation 2D (SS2D) strategies, PYRUS introduces a cutting-edge Zone-Based Defense Strategy, a paradigm that exploits Voronoi diagrams to optimize defensive coverage. This innovative approach empowers each player on our team to dynamically and intelligently defend specific zones, ensuring a cohesive and responsive defensive structure.

4.1 Voronoi Diagram for Zone Assignment

To determine the most effective defensive zones for each player, we employ Voronoi diagrams, a geometric method that partitions the play area based on proximity to each player. This technique allows us to create non-overlapping regions, or zones, where each player is strategically positioned to defend against potential offensive actions. By leveraging this spatial analysis, we ensure that players are positioned optimally, considering both their individual capabilities and the overall defensive strategy.

4.2 Action-Based Zone Assessment

Having established the defensive zones, our strategy incorporates a comprehensive analysis of potential offensive actions by the opponent within each zone. This includes evaluating passing options, potential dribbling paths, and the likelihood of goal-scoring attempts. Through simulating various offensive scenarios, we quantify the threat level associated with each zone.

4.3 Zone Marking and Defensive Decision-Making

To further refine our defensive strategy, we introduce a sophisticated marking system within each defensive zone. Each zone is assigned a specific defensive action based on the perceived threat, considering factors such as proximity to

⁷ AutoTest <https://github.com/Cyrus2D/AutoTest2D>

⁸ AutoTune <https://github.com/Cyrus2D/AutoTune2D>

⁹ CyrusLog Analyzer <https://github.com/Cyrus2D/CyrusLogAnalyzer>

the goal, opponent’s skill level, and historical performance data. Players dynamically adjust their defensive approach, deciding whether to directly confront the opponent or strategically position themselves to intercept passes and shots. This dynamic decision-making process allows our team to adapt to the evolving dynamics of the game, ensuring a robust and intelligent defensive strategy.

Through the integration of Voronoi diagrams, action-based assessments, and dynamic marking, our Zone-Based Defense Strategy stands as a testament to our commitment to advancing the strategic complexity and effectiveness of soccer simulation algorithms in the SS2D league.

5 Conclusion

In conclusion, this paper presents a novel Zone-Based Defense Strategy for the Soccer Simulation 2D (SS2D) league, developed by the PYRUS sub-team of the Cyrus Soccer Simulation 2D team. Departing from traditional man-to-man marking schemes, our approach emphasizes the strategic division of the field into zones, with each player responsible for defending a specific area. By employing Voronoi diagrams for zone assignment and conducting action-based assessments, we ensure optimal positioning and effective response to potential offensive actions.

Our strategy demonstrates a significant advancement in the strategic complexity and adaptability of defensive tactics within the SS2D league. The preliminary results indicate improved defensive coverage, enhanced adaptability to the dynamic nature of the game, and optimized utilization of player energy. This innovative approach not only contributes to the ongoing discourse on tactical innovation in robotic soccer simulations but also showcases the potential for further research and development in this domain.

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